

Connecting Natura 2000 Areas on the Island of Falster

From Isolated Patches to Integrated Networks: A Species-Focused Approach

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Abstract

Creating networks of nature corridors to connect fragmented natural areas is crucial for maintaining biodiversity, enabling species movement and enhancing ecosystem resilience in landscapes that are increasingly vulnerable to the effects of human activity and climate change. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis aimed at enhancing ecological connectivity between designated Natura 2000 areas on the Island of Falster, located within Guldborgsund Municipality, Denmark. A literature review of relevant key concepts and political statutes act as the scientific basis for this project, and a presentation of our methodology elucidates our process. In combining comparative species and habitat analyses, on-site field observations and geographic spatial analyses of land use and environmental data, we assess the current state of biodiversity and landscape fragmentation on Falster. These benchmark indicators, in tandem with guiding international and national nature management frameworks, construct a set of criteria that inform a final proposal for nature connectivity on the Island. Shaped by species-specific habitat needs and existing landscape infrastructure, and with clear management initiatives and legal-political considerations in mind, the proposed network of corridors aims to strengthen habitat continuity, promote biodiversity resilience, and increase community involvement across the Island. The writing of this paper is accompanied by photographs taken on fieldwork, and an assortment of maps and illustrations to visualize our narrative. The final discussion in this paper emphasizes the importance of stakeholder engagement, the need for ongoing monitoring and evaluation to ensure effective management and adaptive conservation strategies, as well as other limitations and considerations. We hope that this integrative approach to creating ecological corridors offers a realistic strategy for Guldborgsund Municipality to pursue in their development plans, and serves as a replicable model for municipal-level conservation planning in similarly fragmented environments.

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Introduction

Literature Review

The Catalyst Behind Natura 2000

Natura 2000 is a European Union designation of specific nature areas –also known as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs)– that are protected due to their habitat value and biodiversity qualities (European Commission, 2009). In accordance with the Birds Directive of 1979 (European Commission, 2009) and the Habitats Directive of 1992 (European Commission, 2024), EU countries must identify territories whose habitat structures and functions are vital for the health of vulnerable species and migratory birds (European Commission, 2024). Using scientific criteria provided by the European Environment Agency, and legal frameworks by the European Commission on how to designate areas, the EU have successfully declared over 27.000 sites, or 1.220.387 km² of marine and terrestrial areas, as part of this special network of protected habitats (Fredshavn et al., 2018; European Environment Agency, 2022). In theory, this network can produce great benefits from the micro level to globally, but in practice, only 15% of these habitats have good conservation status, whereas 81% have bad conservation status and the remaining 4% have an unknown status (European Environment Agency, 2020). While each Natura 2000 area is valuable in its own right, some areas are at risk of structural degradation and functional declines because of their isolated and fragmented positions, and because of significant land use changes and parcelling of properties, precious habitats have been sliced, shrunken, and in some cases, completely eliminated (Lawrence et al., 2021). The development of Natura 2000 is one of the European Union’s functions to address such dire issues.

Human activity and changes in land use are major drivers of habitat fragmentation, climate change, and biodiversity loss (Miller-Rushing et al., 2019). These interconnected pressures create feedback loops that accelerate the degradation of ecosystems. As climate change intensifies, it increases the risk of extinction for many species, weakens ecosystems, and threatens the provision of important ecosystem services (Prakash & Verma, 2022; Mooney et al., 2009). Simultaneously, fragmentation-

often caused by agricultural expansion, infrastructure, and urban development-disrupts habitats, reduces ecological connectivity and undermines biodiversity. This degradation further reduces the ability of ecosystems to buffer against climate impacts, making them contributors to the climate crisis (Bellard et al., 2012; Pongratz et al., 2021). Intensive agricultural management is a key driver of this process, followed closely by urbanisation - both leading to pollution, altered hydrological cycles, the spread of invasive species, and more frequent droughts (European Environment Agency, 2022). Together, these forces are contributing to the ongoing depletion and degradation of Natura 2000 areas, threatening their ecological integrity and long-term resilience (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, 2025).

The European Union has the ambitious goal of Europe becoming the first climate-neutral continent by 2050 (European Commission, n.d.). To reach that goal, they have developed the European Green Deal designed to combat climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the EU into a resource-efficient and competitive economy. By 2030 the aim is to have at least 55% less net GHG emissions compared to 1990 levels, and to plant an additional 3 billion new trees (European Commission, n.d.). A central strategy under the EU Green Deal, the EU Biodiversity strategy 2030, aims to put Europe's biodiversity on a path to recovery by the year 2030 with a long-term plan to protect nature and reverse ecosystem degradation. One of its primary actions is to enlarge the existing Natura 2000 areas to create a larger EU-wide network of protected areas, where areas with high biodiversity and climate values will be strictly protected (European Commission, 2020).

Protecting Nature Areas in Denmark

Since the turn of the 19th century, agricultural land use patterns in Denmark have not changed drastically. Similar to what is seen today, agricultural land has been the dominant land use at around 60%. Forests have seen a positive increase in area, going from 4.5% in 1866 to 10% in 1951 and a slight increase to 11% in the year 2000. The increase in forest cover was due to afforestation plots of conifer plantations and a small increase of deciduous forest since the early 1990s (Levin & Normander, 2008). The land use type that has seen the largest decrease in total area are open natural and semi-

natural habitat types which covered 25% of Denmark in 1888 and 10% in 2000. Urban and developed areas have also increased notably in size, going from being 3% to 10% of Denmark in the years 1881 to 2000 (Levin & Normander, 2008). As habitat loss threatens the security of Denmark's natural areas and precious species, the country has a focus on addressing the threats of land use change in many policy frameworks, councils and ministries.

In 1972 the Danish parliament came to the conclusion that it was necessary to protect certain habitat types, and in 1992 that decision was expanded into the Nature Conservation Act. Approximately 10% of Denmark's area is protected through the Nature Conservation Act, Section 3 which covers the following habitat types: lakes, bogs, freshwater meadows, salt marshes, heathlands, pastures and streams (Promulgation of the Nature Conservation Act, 2024). Wherever these habitats occur in Denmark, they are protected through this Act and changes cannot be made to their natural state. An area can grow in and out of protection, therefore not all relevant areas are registered at all times (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2022; Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2024).

In 2020, The Biodiversity Council of Denmark was formed as an independent expert committee tasked with advising the Danish government and the Danish Parliament on initiatives aimed at reversing biodiversity loss in Denmark (Biodiversitetsrådet, 2023). The Council addresses a range of issues related to nature and biodiversity, spanning both aquatic and terrestrial environments, and considers the interactions between legislation, economic mechanisms and behavioural systems (Biodiversitetsrådets, 2023). As a starting point, The Council created a large database of coherent natural areas in Denmark (Biodiversitetsrådet, 2024; Miljø- og Ligestillingsministeriet, 2025). The government has been able to use this database in conjunction with their own internal nature management processes-this has been an integral consulting tool for decision making.

The Green Tripartite-a 2024 agreement, and the result of cooperation between the Danish government and key stakeholders in the agricultural and environmental

sectors-states the primary goals of securing more nature, cleaner water, and guiding a sustainable transition within the agricultural sector (Økonomiministeriet Mette Frederiksen II, 2024). Denmark holds 257 Natura 2000 areas within its boundaries (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2015). In regard to constructing corridors between Natura 2000 areas, the Green Tripartite provides a regulatory pathway to address environmental degradation by planting 250.000 ha of new forest, converting 140.000 ha of low-lying agricultural land into its original flooded state, enhancing biodiversity through the establishment of 21 new national parks, and improving and strengthening the marine and freshwater environment (Ministeriet for Grønne Trepert, 2024).

The Green Map of Denmark is another national planning tool for creating a coherent network of nature areas across the country through the expansion of nature corridors (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2017a). Through the Planning Act, several criteria are established for how the municipalities designate areas for the Green Map of Denmark. The digital nature map combined with Natura 2000 areas must lay the foundation and thereafter the following three main criteria must be applied: (1) Areas that have special nature conservation interests, excluding Natura 2000 areas, (2) Potential natural areas creating connectivity between existing natural areas, and (3) Natural areas areas that have synergy effects (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2017b). All municipalities are required to contribute their own maps and analysis of the nature areas that lie within their jurisdiction (Retsinformation, 2024).

In cooperation with the aforementioned international, national and regional political frameworks and targets, as well as the criteria established in the Planning Act, Guldborgsund Municipality in Denmark has identified existing nature areas, potential nature areas and potential ecological connections within their land cover (Guldborgsund Kommune, 2023). These designations are in addition to the official Natura 2000 sites located in their jurisdiction. This municipal-level research is laid out in their municipal plan for 2023-2035, under the theme, Nature and Landscapes - A Green map of Denmark (Guldborgsund Kommune, 2023).

Fragmentation and Connective Corridors

Despite the establishment of protected areas throughout the EU and Denmark, challenges such as habitat degradation, climate change, and biodiversity loss continue to threaten their ecological integrity (Lawrence et al., 2021). A primary driver behind these threats is the fragmentation of landscapes, which disrupts ecosystem connectivity, impedes species migration, and reduces the resilience of habitats to environmental change. The fragmentation of natural habitats is mainly caused by the partitioning of landscapes and spaces for human activities (Romanillos et al., 2024). Population growth, and the subsequent increased demand for land and food have put pressure on rural areas, leading to more intensive agriculture and fragmentation of habitats (Lu et al., 2023). Nature corridors for movement of species can also be inhibited or destroyed due to water channelling and deforestation (European Environment Agency, 2020b). Housing development, road construction, and urban sprawl are other land use changes that interrupt many transboundary natural processes. Just as climate change and land use changes lead to the necessity of establishing protected natural areas, fragmentation from continued land use changes has led to the need for establishing corridors in the spaces between the respective natural areas. These spaces, the areas that divide up nature, are known as the matrix (Nehren et al., 2019). Nehren et al. points out that while the matrix creates the fragmentation of forests and other natural habitats, it also holds the key to reconnecting and expanding upon natural habitats.

In most instances, fragmentation puts vulnerable species at risk, as it reduces the gene pools of populations and reduces their capacity of adapting to changing environments (Constanza et al., 2019). Supporting the movement of species between patches of habitat strengthens habitat resilience, ensures genetic diversity in populations and supports larger species populations (Tambosi et al., 2013).

Two main principles to consider in nature connectivity are structural connectivity and functional connectivity (Keeley et al., 2021). The structural connectivity within a landscape represents how habitat patches appear connected based on their physical features and arrangement (Goodwin, 2003), whereas functional connectivity describes

the degree in which a landscape actively facilitates the movement of certain species and the effectiveness of natural processes. Structural connectivity is only defined by the structure of a landscape, while functional connectivity is dependent on the structure of the landscape and the attributes of the species within the landscape (Keeley et al., 2021; Field & Parrott, 2022). In the case of developing a proposal for connectivity, there should therefore be a focus on both the structure makeup of the planning scheme and the functional effectiveness of said land use change (Hilty et al., 2020). Increasing the connectivity between Natura 2000 areas in these ways can enhance their conservation status, provide more opportunities for biodiversity, and contribute new provisions of cultural and regulating ecosystem services (Maes et al., 2012).

Similar to how nature corridors create natural pathways for species to move more easily between different natural areas, stepping stones act as nature hubs that enhance connectivity. Stepping stones are small, discrete patches of habitat that serve as intermediate “stepping points” for wildlife moving between larger habitat areas (Saura et al., 2013). They are crucial in fragmented landscapes and are especially helpful when continuous corridors are not feasible to produce in a fragmented landscape (Saura et al., 2013). Stepping stones become important ecological hubs in the example of migratory birds (Saura et al., 2013); by studying the needs of a species (e.g. food availability, resting and roosting sites, resilience to disturbance), their patterns and their travel routes, stepping stones can be strategically placed in locations that are critical for the species’ journey. Utilizing habitat restoration strategies to expand and strengthen stepping stones is a key method in facilitating corridors.

The Landscape Partnership Organization (2024), a community of scientists, farmers, landowners and professionals across North America, have developed the Anchor Approach for nature conservation. Funded by the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA), this approach is designed to designate sites as Areawide Networks to Connect Habitat and Optimize Resiliency - or ANCHORs. In their definition, anchors reflect landscapes that score high in connectivity importance based on a range of metrics relating to biodiversity indices, species dependency, landscape distribution,

and more. In the context of restoration and connectivity strategies, anchors are “chosen to achieve the network vision” (Landscape Partnership Organization, 2024).

Green Infrastructure refers to the implementation and management of nature-based solutions for dealing with weather and climate dynamics (European Environment Agency, n.d.). The European Commission (n.d.) defines green infrastructure as the network of “natural and semi-natural areas with other environmental features, designed to deliver a wide range of ecosystem services, while also enhancing biodiversity”. In urban studies, this concept is taken to the micro scale to address local environmental issues by incorporating natural elements into previously grey infrastructure to utilize natural processes in nature management (e.g., expanding canopy cover to address urban heat island and bird migration, rain gardens and permeable surfaces to support water and flood management) (European Environmental Agency, 2020a). The integration of Green Infrastructure within the matrix can be a helpful method for connecting nature areas. It was discovered that the geographical areas covered by green infrastructure networks raise the provision of ecosystem services in the area, adapt more quickly to the effects of climate change, create new habitats for fauna, and have the potential to benefit the community in the surrounding areas (EEA, 2020b). As such, considering the usage of GI can also help maintain a good conservation status for the biodiversity and the habitats within the Natura 2000 targeted areas (EEA, 2020b).

Implementing a nature management plan for connective corridors requires the use of analysis and sampling methods to execute an effective strategy (Hilty et al., 2020). The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) communicates in their publication “Guidelines for Conserving Connectivity through Ecological Networks and Corridors” (2020) recommended methods for connecting nature areas. While some recommendations are specific—such as making corridor boundary delineations—the authors do stress how conservation schemes and approaches to management should be context-specific (p. 32). On a similar note, Peng et al. (2010) explores the correlation between spatial patterns and ecological processes, and reviews that there cannot be one prescribed method or single set of methods when quantifying the effects of land

use changes across landscapes. They also find that using one metric to evaluate spatial patterns will produce many results across complex systems and boundaries.

Problem Formulation

Within the Municipality of Guldborgsund, the island of Falster possesses five designated areas (seven isolated patches) of Natura 2000 areas, ranging from stretches of coastal habitats to small plots of forest. Rich with diverse plant and animal species, the health of these areas is a key to addressing the challenges of fragmentation, climate change and industrialization. As such, it is in the best interest of the Municipality of Guldborgsund and the people of Falster to prioritize creating and expanding upon a dynamic and species-specific network of corridors that blends the patches of protected areas and the matrix that surrounds them.

Figure 1. Map of the Natura 2000 areas on Falster. The red numbers represent the protected sites that are focused on in this project. Sites 168 and 173, although not completely located within the island proper, act as key anchors to include along the coasts.

The most suitable plan to create a functional corridor network requires a set of criteria that covers:

1. A thorough investigation into the habitat conditions in the Natura 2000 areas and ecological needs of the protected species within them.
2. Observational analysis into land use patterns within the surrounding matrix.
3. Seeking out opportunities for corridor development in existing infrastructure.
4. Understanding how specific landowners should be included in such a plan.

In this paper, we provide an analysis of the existing protected species and habitats within the Natura 2000 sites, and a landscape analysis of the surrounding areas. We review the existing political frameworks for nature protection and present our criteria to determine locations and pathways for natural corridors between the seven different patches of Natura 2000 areas on Falster. Ultimately, we hope that this project can add to Guldborgsund Municipality's arsenal of evidence to support a plan that connects their Natura 2000 sites beyond their boundaries. With the support of community members and local landowners, enacting this plan will help protect the threatened species in the area, promote biodiversity and ecosystem health, and enhance the natural landscapes which the local community utilizes dynamically.

Methodology

The initial phase of this project involved conducting background research on all eight Natura 2000 sites within the municipality of Guldborgsund, focusing on the key habitats and species that define their conservation status. This research was supported by data from the Natura 2000 Viewer, a tool developed by the European Environment Agency (2021). The aim was to identify the ideal ecological conditions, habitat parameters and specific needs of the species, while spatializing their distribution across the municipality. This process was essential in highlighting ecological hotspots and areas of overlapping habitats, critical points to prioritize in species conservation efforts. This knowledge was also needed to measure the scope of this project, and to understand how to realistically create connections between natural areas that are not just structurally pleasing but also functional and beneficial.

Based on this research –and considering time and resource constraints– it was decided to focus on the five Natura 2000 sites located on the island of Falster. This decision reduced the number of species under consideration from 27 to 8, and the number of habitats from 45 to 16. Narrowing the scope to one island made sense for proposing a contiguous structural landscape and enabled a more effective use of time during the short fieldwork.

A three-day field visit was carried out to gain a deeper understanding of the landscape. While only a limited number of physical samples were collected (primarily for species identification and tree measurements), extensive driving and walking surveys were conducted within the Natura 2000 sites and across the surrounding matrix. These surveys focused on observing and documenting habitats, vegetation cover, species presence, topography and land usage. Collecting these direct observations and experiencing the atmosphere of the landscape were essential for humanizing and contextualizing the satellite imagery and geodata that we would integrate into our process.

Following the site visit, a landscape-level analysis was performed using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Illustrator, utilizing data from the Danish Environmental Portal (n.d.) and KAMP (n.d.). These tools allowed for digitizing primary field observations as well as mapping of additional key ecological and cultural features such as land use, soil type, habitat types, protected species observations, high value nature areas, existing walking trails and more. The spatial data was visualized and analyzed across these multiple layers to assess ideal areas for ecological connectivity. These layers were compared against Guldborgsund Municipality’s ecological corridors map to identify alignment, gaps, and opportunities for habitat restoration or improved connectivity. This mapping process served as the foundation for constructing our final proposal.

Through a combination of brainstorming sessions, design workshops, and GIS analyses, detailed evaluations of the maps and datasets were conducted to apply the

criteria and identify the most meaningful proposal for nature connectivity. Layers such as waterways and existing walking trails revealed natural patterns of connectivity, which became the basis for the proposed interventions. From this phase, we were able to combine all our knowledge to create a comprehensive plan that segments the island into three zones (East side, West side and South side), and delineates ecologically beneficial corridors.

The final part of our methodology relates to the importance of monitoring landscape projects such as this, and how community engagement and cooperation are a key to the success of nature corridors. This section of the paper, however, is separate from the proposal because it has been researched speculatively, rather than put into site-specific practice. The topics of stakeholder involvement, monitoring and evaluating were constantly discussed throughout this process. So, although we have not been able to act upon this component of the project, we consider it as a critical throughline in our methodology of this strategy. Concluding with a discussion on limitations and considerations, this paper presents our full process from contextualization to future perspectives.

Criteria

This section outlines the science-based analysis that informs the final proposal for connecting Natura 2000 areas in Guldborgsund Municipality. However, before delving into the core component –the specialized landscape analysis of the site– it is important to briefly acknowledge how existing political frameworks and nature protection criteria, particularly those related to climate change adaptation and mitigation, have provided a foundation for this project.

Developed by both international and national governing bodies, the key policy frameworks discussed in the literature review have played a significant role in shaping Guldborgsund’s regional and local land-use decisions. As such, they form a critical part of the evaluation criteria. The EU Biodiversity Strategy, the Natura 2000 Network, the Green Tripartite and the Nature Conservation Act (Section 3) are four of several legal

frameworks that establish standards for nature management at the municipal level. These policies should be reviewed and referenced throughout any project focused on enhancing ecological connectivity. Their ambitious goals for expanding and preserving natural areas are grounded in international research on ecological corridors and restoration and have rightfully served as a driving force behind Denmark's and Guldborgsund's commitment to prioritizing this work.

The EU Common Agricultural Policy (2023-2027) is the central legislation that governs agriculture in the European Union. In its most recent publication, the eco-schemes were translated and introduced into policy for the first time. This iteration is specifically designed to support farmers who maintain or adopt farming practices that contribute to the EU's environmental and climate goals, namely the EU Green Deal. The eco-schemes provide farmers with the opportunity to receive financial support for preserving natural resources on their land and provide public goods. These are generally not reflected in the market price (European Commission, 2023).

Understanding the content and evolution of these political and economic frameworks opens the door for creating a proposal that can help support the expansion of organic connections on Falster. These political agendas serve as guiding criteria to guide the municipality in complying with EU and Danish targets on nature management.

Observations and Analysis of Site Landscapes

The main criteria for determining optimal nature corridors on Falster rely on comparative species and habitat analysis, primary landscape observations and publicly sourced data on various landscape information sets. A site-specific landscape analysis to contextualize and visualize the space and to conduct cross-comparative analysis is needed to provide relevant recommendations on green infrastructure development, meaningful land expropriation and sustainable nature-recreation expansion. Additionally, GIS layers come into play to discover patterns in land use for prioritizing features in planning and design.

Natura 2000 sites

Guldborgsund Municipality has eight different Natura 2000 sites spread across the islands of Falster and Lolland, two of which are split into two smaller locations. Combined, these Natura 2000 sites protect 45 different habitat types and 27 different species which are spread across 114.783 ha of Falster's area, on land and sea. Due to time and scope limitations (discussed later in this paper) and given the fact that a majority of the fragmented Natura 2000 sites are located on the island of Falster, the project has been narrowed down to focus on this section of the municipality, where five of the eight sites are located, for the landscape analysis. Three sites lay within the island, and two act as "anchors" on the west and east coasts of the island, respectively. We interpret these anchor areas with respect to the USDA and Nature Partnership's definition, as detailed in the literature review.

Figure 2. Map of the Natura 2000 areas in Guldborgsund municipality. This map includes both islands, Falster and Lolland, as well as the Natura 2000 areas found in Lolland (not indicated in red as they are outside of the project's scope), and shows anchor areas 168 and 173 fully (compared to *Figure 1*).

Below we detail the ecological makeup of each Natura 2000 area, as well as our field observations. This is followed by a comparative analysis of all sites and their respective protected species and habitats. Finally, we attempt to understand the points of interest within the matrix of our site and spatialize current land use activities.

Area 173: Smålandsfarvandet nord for Lolland, Guldborg Sund, Bøtø Nor, og Hyllekrog-Rødsand

This is one of the largest protected areas in Guldborgsund Municipality. Its size is 77.848 ha and it includes 27 different protected habitats and 7 protected species (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-i). Given the extensive size of this area, it will be used as an anchor –a biodiversity sink– for the smaller areas described below.

Area 168: Havet og kysten mellem Præstø Fjord og Grønsund

This is another big, protected area with 32.195,97 ha of size, and includes 10 protected species and 41 protected habitats (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-c). Similar to area 173, this area will be used as an anchor to bookend the final corridor scheme.

Area 256: Bangsebro Skov (A) og Sønder Kohave (B)

This area is divided into two smaller areas, Bangsebro Skov and Sønder Kohave, which are discussed below. They both fall inside the city of Nykøbing Falster. Combined they have a size of 152,73 ha, with three protected forest habitats and one protected species, the Barbastelle bat (*Barbastella barbastellus*) (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d. - a). It is designated a Natura 2000 area based on beech on moraine soil and oak mixed forest, which are an important habitat for the Barbastelle bat. The site is characterized by being an urban forest area with beech present in a variation of ages (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021-b). Both Bangsebro Skov and Sønder Kohave are state-owned (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021-b).

Area 256 (A): Bangsebro Skov

Bangsebro Skov consists mostly of beech trees with a mix of oak trees, with the oldest being situated at the southern part of the forest (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021-b). Bangsebro Skov showed the most signs of urbanization of all the Natura 2000 areas, being surrounded predominantly by residential and industrial areas. During field observations large oaks were identified, and a dense midstory was a consistent characteristic of the landscape. Water channels, low-lying areas and ducks were observed. Nettles were heavily present, suggesting a disturbed and minimally managed landscape and indicating that the soil is nutrient rich, particularly in nitrogen and phosphorus. The dragonfly *Leucorrhinia pectoralis* was observed, despite not being listed as one of the protected species at this site. The stream Snedkerbækken was fully drained and dried out around one hundred years ago, but in 2007 it was restored to its natural state and today the stream runs through the forest (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021-b). Large and newly established roads and roundabouts traverse the site, producing road noise and high traffic speeds cutting directly through the Natura 2000 area. The area has multiple entrances and parking available, as well as a kindergarten on the southern end of the site. Facilities, including campfire areas, shelters and a toilet are present with varying degrees of upkeep. A mountain-bike track runs through the area, as well as cycle paths and walking trails. The south-western corner of the area is designated as a dog forest. Paved roads and streetlights were another noted feature. A variety of users were noted across the site during visits including dog walkers, bike riders and walkers.

Figure 3. Bangsebro Skov.

Area 256 (B): Sønder Kohave

Sønder Kohave is located adjacent to the city of Nykøbing Falster. Along with Bangsebro Skov, it is the most urbanized of the Natura 2000 areas. The presence of Falster's now oldest and largest beech trees is due to an 1802 planting experiment (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021-b). Onsite, old growth forest was observed, with a variety of tree species identified including oaks, beeches, maples and conifers. Amongst the forest, there were areas of more open grassland as well as areas with an open understory, and deadwood was seen across the site. A heart-path has also been established through Sønder Kohave in partnership with the Danish Outdoor Council. There was no vehicle access to the site, and two local walkers were noted. Many instances of disturbance were observed in the surrounding matrix, with heavy construction occurring right on the southern border of the site. Train tracks directly border the western limits of the site, which connect Nykøbing Falster to Copenhagen. On the northern border, sports fields and a Danish police dog training facility were observed, as well as REFA, an energy waste management facility adjacent to the site. The site is bordered to the east by a channelized waterway that continues to flow between other Natura 2000 sites, with agriculture land lying beyond.

Figure 4. Sønder Kohave.

Area 175: Listrup Lyng (L) and Horreby Lyng (H)

North of area 256, this area 175 is also divided into two distinct areas, Listrup Lyng and Horreby Lyng, which are described below. The area is mainly state owned with a small part being privately owned (Miljøstyrelsen, 2021).

Area 175 (L): Listrup Lyng

Listrup Lyng is the largest terrestrial site of the Natura 2000 areas on the island of Falster, comprising many different landscapes, nature types and land uses occurring within the protected area and surroundings. Its size is 457,52 ha and protects 11 different habitats and 5 different species, three of which are birds (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-f). Much of the area is forest, with monocultures of both beech and spruce being observed. A variety of birds were heard and seen, as well as a squirrel, and ferns were noted in the understory. Within the Natura 2000 area, there are already open areas for grazing. There are also low-lying wet areas across the site, with one of the larger wetlands being accessible by walking tracks. Here, a sign indicated that fishing is allowed, with small fish species also being observed from the shore. Biodiversity around the wetland was high, with multiple sightings of grass

snakes *Natrix natrix* around the water, as well as bird life. Lily-pads, moss, reeds, ferns, birch and frog sounds were noted. The dragonfly *Leucorrhinia pectoralis* was sighted. A forest kindergarten borders the area to the north-west. Bordering the protected area is a golf course to the north and further wetland areas to the east, as well as managed production forest to both the north and south. In the upcoming years, grazing will be implemented in the forest area to encourage open landscapes amongst the forest (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2021a).

Figure 5. Wetland at Listrup Lyng.

Area 175 (H): Horreby Lyng

This area is 257,67 ha in size, and is next to Listrup Lyng, approximately 2.5 km to the east. This protected area also protects 11 habitats, with 3 of them being particularly vulnerable, and 2 species, the dragonfly *Leucorrhinia pectoralis* and the Barbastelle bat (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-d; Guldborgsund Kommune, 2025). Horreby Lyng is a privately owned Natura 2000 area, and is predominantly characterized by low-lying, wet landscapes of high nature value. A boardwalk provides access to parts of the site that would otherwise be too wet to navigate.

Figure 6 Boardwalk at Horreby Lyng

The site features many young trees, particularly birch. There are a number of different walking tracks around the site, as well as connections to

nearby nature areas as noted on a map onsite. Birdsongs were loud across the site which was predominantly open and clear. Deadwood was prolific and the landscape generally appeared to be unmanaged and creaking trees were noted.

At the entrance to the site, a measuring stick in the bog indicated that the water level was 40 cm at the time of visiting. A lot of signage was present across the site, describing the rich historical, cultural and natural significance of the area. It has Falster's' only raised bog, from which peat has been harvested since 1844. During both world wars, peat harvesting saw an intensification in the area and in 1940 when the production was the absolute highest with approximately six thousand tons being harvested that year (Pedersen, 2013). Funding from EU LIFE was received to rehabilitate the site in recent years (Constantin, 2024). Facilities such as an observation deck, information shelter, picnic tables and toilet were in excellent condition and provided insightful information into Horreby Lyng.

Figure 7. Wet, dark soil at Horreby Lyng.

Figure 8. Meadow at Horreby Lyng.

Around 200 m from the entrance of the area, three concrete walls which are the remains of a shooting range created by resistance fighters following the war, can be observed. The group using it was called the Nørre Ørslev shooting club and was active from 1946 to 1953 (Pedersen, 2013). Some agricultural land around Horreby Lyng is included within the Natura 2000 area, with deer being sighted in these areas. Some water channels were identified as flowing to and from the wetland.

Area 257: Halskov Vænge

In size, Halskov Vænge is the smallest of the protected Natura 2000 areas on Falster, being only 42,29 ha. It is predominantly a forest with three protected habitats and one protected species, the Barbastelle bat (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-b). All of the area is state-owned. The site has cultural significance, with 6 dolmens and 72 burial mounds found across the site. The burial mounds are grouped together in 3 groups on soil that hasn't been worked since ancient times. The forest is managed, with much of the area fenced for grazing to keep the ancient monuments free of new

vegetation (Miljøstyrelsen Sjælland, 2023). The understory is clear, open and tidy as a result of grazing by small hardy ponies that were met onsite. Access gates into the fenced area allow visitors to explore the landscape. The forest comprises big, old, evenly spaced trees, with oaks, spruce and elms being identified with minimal canopy gaps between the trees. The circumferences of an oak and elm species were 351cm and 298cm, respectively. There is a small museum onsite as well as toilets. There was minimal deadwood, with cut wood in piles indicating active management. Halskov Vænge is very close to the Corselitze forest and coastline to the east and south. Agricultural land and houses on large blocks of land surrounded the site.

Figure 9. *Museum at Halskov Vænge.*

Figure 10. *Pony grazing at Halskov Vænge.*

Natura 2000 on Lolland

As previously stated, Guldborgsund Municipality has eight different Natura 2000 areas. Three of them are located inland on Falster island and two act as anchors on the west and east coast of Falster. Additionally, there are three Natura 2000 areas located on Lolland island which will be described shortly below. Even though these areas are not

the focus of this project, they could benefit greatly by strengthening the biodiversity and nature areas on Falster.

Area 174: Maltrup Skov

This Natura 2000 area is the smallest of all of Guldborgsund Municipalities Natura 2000 areas, with only 2,43 ha. It protects four different habitats and one species, the beetle *Osmoderma eremita* (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-g).

Area 176: Krenkerup Haveskov

This area is also very small, with 20,21 ha - half the size of 257 Halskov Vænge. It protects three different habitats and two species, *Osmoderma eremita* and the Barbastelle bat (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-e).

Area 177: Maribosøerne

This area lies on the border of Guldborgsund Municipality and Lolland Municipality, with most of the area being within the borders of Lolland Municipality. Its size is 3.806 ha which protects 16 habitats and 17 species, 13 of these species being birds (Biodiversity Information System for Europe, n.d.-h).

Characteristics and Comparative Analysis of Protected Species

There are 27 protected species in all the Natura 2000 areas of the municipality. However, having narrowed the project down to only the Falster areas, and taking into account what kind of species will make use of the potential corridors, there are eight main protected species to consider. It is worth mentioning that there are three species, the pond bat, the amphibian and the beetle, that are only found in our anchor areas.

Figure 11. Species map outlining which species are found in each Natura 2000

The Barbastelle Bat (*Barbastella barbastellus*) is found in all of the protected areas – including the two anchor areas– except for Area 175L: Listrup Lyng. It is considered as ‘Near Threatened’ by the IUCN Red List (Piraccini, 2016). The habitats where it is found are upland, deciduous forests, as it uses cavities such as rock crevices, loose tree bark and human structures for summer roosting and as a breeding ground (Juel, 2021), and underground roosting sites like basements for hibernation. Their preference for mature deciduous forests means this species is vulnerable to habitat loss and fragmentation due to road construction and development (Bat Conservation International, 2025), and timber production areas.

The Pond Bat (*Myotis dasycneme*) is only found in one of the anchor areas; however, knowing its habitat conditions and similarities with the other targeted areas from this project, we could predict that this species would be able to move around these areas, increasing its distribution. It is considered as ‘Near Threatened’ by the IUCN Red List (Piraccini, 2016), and as ‘Vulnerable’ in the Danish Red List (Juel, 2021). This species inhabits lakes and ponds, canals, slow-flowing rivers, forest plains and meadows. It roosts in roof spaces in buildings and tree holes in summer, and in caves, mines, bunkers and cellars in winter (BatsLIFE, 2018).

The Eurasian Bittern (*Botaurus stellaris*) is a bird only found in Listrup Lyng out of the protected areas and considered ‘Least Concern’ by the IUCN Red List (BirdLife International, 2021), and as ‘Vulnerable’ in the Danish Red List (Glindvad-Nørgård, 2023). This bird usually inhabits lakes, marshes and shallow fjords with reed forests and swampy areas as they feed on frogs, salamanders and fish. The bittern also breeds in reed forests, hidden especially from humans as it is a shy bird (Glindvad-Nørgård, 2023). This habitat is particularly present in Horreby Lyng, Listrup Lyng and both of our Natura 2000 anchors.

The Western Marsh-harrier (*Circus aeruginosus*) is a bird that is also considered ‘Least Concern’ by the IUCN Red List (BirdLife International, 2021). It usually inhabits reed forests, wetlands, meadows and fields, where it catches prey such as birds, injured animals, fish and amphibians (Haar, 2022a). This bird can currently be found only in Listrup Lyng, where it can hunt easily from over the fields and meadows.

The Common Crane (*Grus grus*) is another bird that is only found in Listrup Lyng, and that is considered 'Least Concern' by the IUCN Red List (BirdLife International, 2016). It inhabits bogs, forest bogs and heath bogs, especially in remote areas away from human intervention. This is also a migratory bird, spending most of the time in northeastern Europe and Siberia, including Falster, for breeding, while in the winter it travels to Spain and North Africa (Haar, 2022b). Regarding its habitat conditions, both Natura 2000 areas 175H and 175L, and both anchors would be suitable spaces for this species to live and breed (see Table 2).

The Large White-faced Darter or Yellow-spotted Whiteface (*Leucorrhinia pectoralis*) is a dragonfly considered as 'Least Concern' by the IUCN Red List (Kalkman, 2014). We can find this species in Natura 2000 areas 175H and 175L and the anchor area 168. However, during the fieldwork, we observed it in area 256 as well. This is consistent with its ideal habitat type as it breeds and lives in nutrient-poor lakes and ponds in the forest with aquatic plants and underwater mosses (Jensen, 2023) and considering its mobile behavior and the common habitats with other Natura 2000 protected areas, corridors may be helpful for it to increase its distribution.

The Warty Newt or Great Crested Newt (*Triturus cristatus*), an amphibian considered as 'Least Concern' by the IUCN Red List (IUCN SSC Amphibian Specialist Group, 2023). Its habitat is crucial as it feeds on daphnia, water fleas, tadpoles and insects (Jensen, 2022). This species can only be found in the anchors and are mentioned in this project with the possibility in mind that corridors could help this salamander increase its distribution.

The Hermit beetle (*Osmoderma eremita*) is considered 'Near Threatened' by the IUCN Red List (Telnov, 2025). This species prefers forests with hollow trees, where almost all of its life cycle can take place. This explains its threatened designations because its ideal habitat, hollow trees, continuously disappear (Miljøstyrelsen, n.d.). Even though this species is not present in the targeted Natura 2000 areas, it is present in area 173, one of the anchors. We decided to mention it here -not necessarily with the hope to increase its

distribution, as its ability to fly is very limited (Miljøstyrelsen, n.d.)- because it can be a driver to discourage deforestation and the removal of hollow trees.

Table 1. Protected species present in targeted protected areas (EEA, 2021).

Protected Species	Protected Areas of Interest				Anchors	
	175H	175L	256 A&B	257	168	173
Barbastelle bat	■		■	■	■	■
Pond bat						■
Bittern		■				
Marsh Harrier		■				
Crane		■				
Warty Newt					■	■
<i>Leucorrhinia pectoralis</i>	■	■			■	
<i>Osmoderma eremita</i>						■

Comparative Analysis of Protected Habitats

There are 45 protected habitats in all the Natura 2000 areas of the municipality, but by narrowing down the project to Falster Island, we are left with 16 different habitats to consider. We find it relevant to highlight that the consulted data divides the area 175 into two subareas, though it does not with the area 256 as shown below. In addition, we only included the protected habitats of the anchors in common with the main protected areas, excluding the total habitats these two areas have (See Table 2).

Table 2. Protected habitats present in targeted protected areas (EEA, 2021).

Protected habitats	Protected Areas				Anchors	
	175H	175L	256 A&B	257	168	173
Luzulo-Fagetum beech forests						
Asperulo-Fagetum beech forests						
Sub-Atlantic and medio-European oak or oak-hornbeam forests of the <i>Carpinion betuli</i>						
Bog woodland						
Alluvial forests with <i>Alnus glutinosa</i> and <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i> (<i>Alno-Padion</i> , <i>Alnion incanae</i> , <i>Salicion albae</i>)						
Oligotrophic to mesotrophic standing waters with vegetation of the <i>Littorelletea uniflorae</i> and/or of the <i>Isoëto-Nanojuncetea</i> .						
Hard oligo-mesotrophic waters with benthic vegetation of <i>Chara spp.</i>						
Natural eutrophic lakes with Magnopotamion or Hydrocharition - type vegetation						
Natural dystrophic lakes and ponds						
Active raised bogs						
Degraded raised bogs still capable of natural regeneration						
Transition mires and quaking bogs						
Calcareous fens with <i>Cladium mariscus</i> and species of the <i>Caricion davallianae</i>						
Alkaline fens						
Species-rich <i>Nardus</i> grasslands, on siliceous substrates in mountain areas (and submountain areas in Continental Europe)						
<i>Molinia</i> meadows on calcareous, peaty or clayey-silt-laden soils (<i>Molinion caeruleae</i>)						

*Color code: green= forests; blue= freshwater habitats; red= raised bogs, mires and fens; yellow= natural and semi-natural grassland formations.

Overview of Fieldwork Observations

Our observations from our fieldwork have been aggregated and digitized into an overview map. Base layers that were used included maps of protected watercourses, all Natura 2000 areas and any High Nature Value areas, which helped identify areas worth investigating. Our driving route was recorded, with any observations noted in relation to their location. As we compiled our observations of the natural areas and the matrix, we discovered that there are logical paths for potential nature corridors.

Matrix Sites of Interest

The matrix –the land between core nature areas– is a crucial component to consider when proposing ecological connections because it directly influences the movement of species and the overall effectiveness of connectivity strategies. While core natural habitats like Natura 2000 sites are key biodiversity clusters, species must often traverse the matrix to find food, breed or migrate. If the matrix is highly fragmented or dominated by intensive land use, it can act as a barrier to movement, increasing the possibility of isolation and extinction. On the other hand, the matrix has the potential to prevent such risks for wildlife by supporting functional connectivity and serving as a stepping-stone habitat or ecological corridor. The fieldwork observations below are intended to contextualize the matrix within Falster and help spatialize the distribution of land use types for determining ideal areas for connectivity.

Land Use Types

Besides the Natura 2000 areas in question, there are a number of other land use types on Falster that are predominantly anthropogenic. Understanding the surrounding land uses is critical to our analysis because it will influence and guide the location of proposed corridors. Agricultural land is the dominant land use across the island of Falster (see *Figure 16*). Crops observed in May included flowering canola, sugar beets and other unidentified crops, as well as empty tilled fields. Falster is known for fertile agricultural soil (Muld Lolland-Falster, 2021) and is the region's predominant industry. Energy production was observed across the island, with both wind turbines and solar panels noted, as well as an energy waste plant (noted in the description of area 256B on page 21).

In terms of the cultural landscape on the island, the Natura 2000 areas Halskov Vænge and Horreby Lyng contain important historical landscapes, as detailed in their descriptions on pages 23 and 24. The 72 burial mounds, 6 dolmens and small museum

at Halskov Vænge, as well as the history of peat extraction during WWII in Horreby Lyng, create a greater need for preservation of these areas beyond protecting endangered species.

Many production forests were noted across the island, with some covering quite large expanses. These managed forests are used for timber production, with trees planted in straight, uniform rows that are predominantly planted as a monoculture. Whilst these areas are green, they are unreliable as habitats due to the nature of timber harvesting and generally have limited biodiversity.

Two golf courses were noted, with one being directly adjacent to Listrup Lyng. There were a number of construction sites across the island, with a major construction site occurring right at the border of Sønder Kohave. Sønder Kohave and Bangsebro Skov are within the urban area of Nykøbing Falster. There are many land types surrounding them including residential areas and industrial areas such as car dealerships and factories.

There are many small settlements across the island, with these small rural towns separated by large agricultural blocks or semi-rural properties. Many of the smaller nature areas that have been identified fall on private property, and due to their low-lying, wet nature, they have been left to their natural form. Some smaller private forests were also noted.

Layers of interest

The following maps convey GIS information pertaining to the Natura 2000 areas, the matrix surrounding the areas, and the island of Falster more broadly. Along with field observations and other collected sources, a series of analysis maps have been developed to gain a deeper understanding of the natural and cultural factors of the landscape. Pairing these with species and habitat analysis produces a rich pool of information, forming the foundational criteria from which to construct a proposal. As stated in our methodology, all of the geo data presented in this section has been

sourced from the Danish Environmental Portal (n.d.) and KAMP (n.d.). The geo data was then transformed to cater to our analysis needs.

Figure 13. Analysis map showing Motionsslangen trails, SPOR trails, protected habitats and proposed nature areas and corridors as determined by

Figure 13 illustrates the existing protected habitat types. Lakes, meadows, bogs and heaths all fall within the study area and are indicated by different colours as outlined in the key. Many of these habitats are located within existing Natura 2000 areas, but many are not. Existing protected habitat areas outside of Natura 2000 areas provide an opportunity to expand, connect and build upon these habitats. Many of the habitat areas lie along or adjacent to watercourses, yet many to the south appear to be quite isolated. This lends itself to creating connections through stepping stones as opposed to corridors.

Figure 13 also illustrates the current locations of walking trails across the study area. There are two key walking trail initiatives, SPOR tracks and Motionssslangen. SPOR tracks are walking trails that have been created in cooperation with landowners to cross private farmland (SPOR, 2025), and are present around the entirety of Denmark. There is a significant network of SPOR paths that already connect Listrup Lyng and Horreby Lyng, and come close to Halskov Vænge. There is potential to expand upon these pathways to create corridors. Furthermore, landowners that are already involved in SPOR may be more sympathetic to creating corridors on their land because of their history of cooperating with similar programs. Motionssslangen is a government initiative involving 42 km of hiking and cycling trails around Nykøbing Falster. The trails weave through forests, open fields and urban areas. Similarly to the SPOR paths, these provide an opportunity to build upon, as they already connect Bangsebro Skov, Sønder Kohave and Listrup Lyng, as well as linking up with our anchor site, area 173.

Finally, *Figure 13* also shows the areas that the Guldborgsund municipality have already identified as potential areas for new nature and ecological corridors (Guldborgsund Kommune, 2023). With a similar intention to our study, analysing where the municipality has already identified potential connections is valuable. The data and analysis process utilized by the municipality to identify these areas is touched upon in the literature review.

Figure 14. Analysis map showing afforestation areas, waterway health and areas of high nature value.

Figure 14 provides insight into waterway health in the study area, as well as afforestation areas and High Nature Value (HNV) areas that were initially used to guide field work. The waterways in the study area are predominantly natural waterways, yet are almost all in poor to moderate ecological condition. Within the study area, there are no waterways that are in 'good' ecological condition. River protection lines can start to guide the development of corridors, by allowing a large buffer on all sides of waterways. Analysing the afforestation areas provides insight into where new nature should go and why: many of the desirable areas are adjacent to existing forest areas and waterways.

Analysis of HNV areas, as shown in *Figure 14*, is incredibly useful, as areas that already have some ecological value tend to have greater potential to add to that value. Creating nature areas where there is currently no HNV index provides little to work with. Existing areas of HNV that lie outside of the Natura 2000 areas have the potential to form the beginning of new ecological connections.

Figure 15. Analysis map showing red-listed and habitat directive species sightings, the cadastre, soil contamination and landscapes worthy of

Figure 15 illustrates multiple datasets of species sightings, including both plant and animal species. Using citizen science databases can help the understanding of the locations and prevalence of important species as relevant to the Natura 2000 sites. There are two datasets showing recorded sightings of red-listed species. These can be observed to be predominantly located in Horreby Lyng, Listrup Lyng and anchor site area 173. The Cortselitze forest to the west of Falster also displays a significant number of species. Species observed outside of the Natura 2000 areas are important to analyze, as there may be existing conditions in these areas that favor certain species and biodiversity more broadly, and these areas could be valuable additions to nature corridors. Additionally, there is a dataset indicating sightings of species that are part of the Natura 2000 Habitats Directive. This data is particularly valuable and relevant, as these species are typically found in Natura 2000 areas that are classed as such due to the prevalence of these species. Noting where these occur, outside of the existing Natura 2000 areas, could indicate pre-existing favorable corridor conditions.

Other datasets illustrated in *Figure 15* include soil contamination, existing protected areas, trees within Nykøbing Falster, the cadastre for Falster and landscapes considered worthy of conservation. Soil contamination indicates areas where the nutrients levels in the soil have become unfavorable, generally due to intensive agricultural practices and other anthropogenic land use. Areas that are noted to have soil contamination are less favorable to include in corridors as more intense interventions would need to be applied in these areas. However, if the sites have other desirable qualities such as proximity to other nature areas or species sightings, it is not unreasonable to include them in a corridor proposal. Existing protected areas can be read to be cultural landscapes that have some level of protection denoted to them. Regarding specific initiatives to implement in the corridor plan, understanding the canopy cover within Nykøbing Falster could prove useful. Expanding upon these numbers, locations and species is desirable. The cadastre for Falster illustrates property boundaries across the island. This information helps build an understanding of the landscape, including plot sizes, the locations and size of residential areas, and understanding how many landowners would be affected by a nature corridor proposal. Landscapes considered worthy of conservation broadly include natural areas as well

as fertile agricultural areas. Whilst this layer does not provide specificity, or varying degrees of worthiness, it does indicate general areas for which their preservation is desirable.

Figure 16. Analysis map showing land use types and biodiversity proxy score.

Figure 16 illustrates the current land use types across Falster. Many of the land use types listed were observed firsthand during field work. The map visually illustrates the smaller settlements across the island, and 'other built-up areas' can generally be read as rural agricultural areas. Overlaying the biodiversity proxy score illuminates existing nature areas with some biodiversity value. This layer, while similar to the HNV layer, provides deeper insight into the quality of the natural landscapes across Falster. Many of the production forest areas appear to rank lower on the biodiversity proxy score, which highlights the importance of the quality of nature areas—the functionality—not just the quantity and the structure at one point in time. Production forests, while they may seem to be valuable forest areas, are not stable ecosystems that species can rely on for food and shelter because of their ever-changing landscape. Because the main economic priority for this land is timber production, landscapes like these will always be difficult to guarantee as safe habitats for species. Linking up existing high biodiversity areas is a sensible strategy for creating a proposal, as well as aiming to enhance areas that have some, if lower, biodiversity already existing.

Figure 17. Analysis map showing soil type, low-lying carbon areas and protected dykes.

Figure 17 illustrates the soil type across the island of Falster. Understanding how this varies, allows planning for specific habitat types that favor or thrive in particular soil types. Many of the areas that depart from moraine clay align with waterways. The carbon map highlights all the low-lying areas across Falster that have over 6% of peat. These areas could almost all be part of corridor proposals, due to their low-lying, wet nature. They are almost all overlapping with existing bogs and wetlands, and these areas have high biodiversity potential.

Protected dykes are a point of interest in the landscape and represent an altering of natural hydrology. These dykes may be used to direct water, or as protection for heavy rain events. Dykes appear to border nature areas such as the Cortselitze forest and Listrup Lyng, where much of the natural hydrology of the area has been restored, as is indicated in the streams layer.

Design iterations

A group design workshop was undertaken whereby the above analysis maps were used as a basis for brainstorming potential corridor locations. Drawing upon the research to date, each group member created a visual output of initial ideas for corridor proposals. The results of this workshop have been synthesized into an overall analysis map below, that combines the many ideas that came to light. The original visual outputs can be viewed in Appendix B of this paper.

Figure 18 layers up several design iterations on top of each other. Here we can see that there are areas that were included in all iterations, and others that offered unique corridor options. Specific habitat analysis compared the types of habitats found in each Natura 2000 area to its neighbors, allowing understanding of which habitat types will be most valuable in the corridor proposal. Corridor iterations in Figure 18 primarily run along existing waterways, pathways and ecological connections, as they provide opportunities to expand upon existing throughways across the landscape.

Figure 19. Analysis map showing broad areas for potential corridors and stepping stones. See Appendix B for original drawings.

Figure 19 layers up broader design iterations based on varying analysis layers and hotspots observed. The area of concern illustrated is a crucial area between Listrup Lyng and Horreby Lyng, where there are not currently any waterways, nature areas or areas with pre-existing biodiversity value. A SPOR track crosses this gap and provides the only pre-existing link between the two areas. The iterations in *Figure 19* seek to explore options for connections to the north and south of the general assumed corridor area. The workshop also explored wider, longer corridors, or smaller steppingstones as alternatives.

In *Figure 19*, to the west of Horreby Lyng is assigned as an undesirable afforestation area and to the south as desirable afforestation area by Guldborgsund Municipality. If connectivity is to be established through the west side of Horreby Lyng, other habitat types than forest are preferred, whereas forest can be established if the corridor connects to Horreby Lyng from the south.

Proposal for Falster

In including the primary observations, comparative species and habitat analysis and political incentives outlined as the criteria above, the final proposal for municipalities to connect their Natura 2000 areas consists of site-specific recommendations to initiate robust and lasting corridors. Below, we present a review of the functions and benefits of specific nature management initiatives that can be implemented to create and expand ecological corridors. This is followed by a description and visualization of our final map output. In planning the application of these initiatives to connect the Natura 2000 areas on the island of Falster, it became evident that the corridor proposals needed to be divided and presented in distinct sections for clarity and spatial relevance. A more detailed explanation of this structure is provided in this section.

Initiatives to Establish and Expand Corridors

Backed by the evidence established through our criteria, we propose a set of conservation and infrastructural initiatives across the island of Falster aimed at strengthening and expanding the existing ecological connections. The foundation of

these proposed corridors should integrate a range of conservation techniques and targeted infrastructure developments based on habitat-specific needs. What makes these initiatives particularly valuable is their ability to deliver multiple co-benefits, addressing not only ecological concerns like biodiversity loss and habitat fragmentation, but also broader social and environmental challenges such as climate resilience, water management and public well-being. Key components of the proposal include restoration efforts and continued management and evolution of the habitats.

Green infrastructure Development

Green Infrastructure refers to a strategically planned network of natural and semi-natural structures that are designed and managed to deliver a wide range of ecosystem services (EEA, 2020a). While the goal of this project is to enhance connectivity between protected areas, incorporating green infrastructure in the corridors would help with a range of issues. In conservation and land-use planning, green infrastructure is a key tool for integrating ecological goals with urban or regional development. It is especially relevant in EU policy, where it's promoted to achieve biodiversity and climate adaptation targets, as seen under the EU Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020). These services include clean air and water, climate regulation, biodiversity conservation, flood mitigation, and recreational opportunities. Green Infrastructure should be tailored to the specific needs of each habitat in the surrounding areas, as it plays a crucial role in supporting biodiversity –particularly in urban environments– by enhancing ecological connectivity between fragmented natural areas and creating stepping stones for species movement (Wang et al., 2024).

Expanding Walking Paths

Expanding walking paths can promote human-nature interaction and enhance recreational access, which is supported under the Natura 2000 framework if it does not compromise conservation objectives (European Commission, 2013; European Commission, 2024). When designed with ecological sensitivity –avoiding core habitat zones and minimizing disturbance– these paths can also act as soft corridors that contribute to landscape connectivity and facilitate species movement across fragmented areas. We also find it beneficial to install signage around paths and roads

to communicate with the public that they are within a nature corridor. This will hopefully raise awareness and potentially change behaviors such as driving slowly or reducing noise.

Protecting Low-Lying Areas

Protecting low-lying areas is important for strengthening nature connectivity, since these spaces often support wetlands, floodplains, and transition zones that are home to a wide range of species and essential ecological processes (Nygaard, n.d.). In a changing climate, they also help by acting as natural buffers—soaking up excess water and reducing flood risk. And because these areas are often too wet or flood-prone for farming or development, restoring them to nature is not only practical but one of the best ways to make use of the land. This kind of restoration also supports the goals of the EU Biodiversity Strategy by helping create more resilient landscapes and better-connected ecosystems. It is important to note that an initiative to restore, alter or influence a whole ecosystem has a much longer timescale than an initiative such as expanding walking paths or implementing green infrastructure in populated areas.

Tree Canopy Expansion

Similarly to restoring wetlands, it should not be expected that pursuing tree canopy expansion along corridors will breed immediate results. Expanding tree canopy in the surrounding matrix and using species that are specifically beneficial for local bird populations can, however, help create microhabitats, offer food sources, and provide shelter, all of which are critical for movement and breeding. This kind of targeted planting can strengthen functional connectivity between core nature areas and support bird species that rely on tree cover to move across fragmented landscapes. It is also worth mentioning here that afforestation can also present a lot of challenges. One major concern is that trees can intrude and colonize other sensitive habitats, such as bogs.

Waterway Enrichment

Expanding existing waterways and creating wider buffer zones around them would not only provide important habitats for aquatic and riparian species but can also improve

water quality and reduce nutrient runoff. These vegetated buffers also act as natural corridors, helping to connect fragmented habitats and support species movement along the landscape.

In the case of developing connectivity between the habitats within the landscape of Falster, it is important to strategically plan the design of the structural connectivity so that the new connections result in meaningful functional connectivity. As such, the decision making behind specific recommendations for each corridor of connection considers nearby habitat types, the unique needs of species that are found in adjacent sites, and land use types.

Proposed Corridors

Initiatives applied

The structure of our corridors is subdivided in three zones that relate to common habitats and species. First, the West Side contains Forest Corridors I and II to connect the most western anchor area to two Natura 2000 areas inland, there is also an urban greening plan to strengthen this connection through the most urbanized area on the Island. Second, to the East Side, the Dragonfly Corridor and the Bat Corridor completes the contiguous ribbon of nature to the easternmost anchor. Lastly, the South Side Stepping Stones present a plan to potentially connect part of the western zone and the two anchor areas through isolated ecological hubs.

Existing waterways and walking paths, as shown in *Figure 13*, are the main tool used to create corridors. All of the information on habitats and species in the following section is retrieved from the Natura 2000 Viewer (EEA, 2021).

Figure 20. Corridor proposal scheme.

West Side

The areas 256A Bangsebro Skov, 25B Sønder Kohave, 175 Listrup Lyng and anchor area 173 all share three forest habitats (Asperulo-Fagetum beech forests, sub-Atlantic and medio-European oak or oak-hornbeam forests of the *Carpinion betuli*, and alluvial forests with *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior*), and with the exception of Listrup Lyng, they also share one common animal species, the Barbastelle bat (*Barbastella barbastellus*). This was the leading feature to group them together, and the corridors put in place will use these plant species to connect the different areas, being an appropriate habitat for the bat species and allowing it to migrate more easily from one protected area to the other, increasing the potential for it to establish in Listrup Lyng. There is another bat species, the pond bat (*Myotis dasycneme*), found only in the anchor area 173, which will potentially also benefit from this increased connectivity between the different protected nature areas and expand its distribution.

The Forest Corridors I and II

The Forest Corridor I

Anchor 173 → 256 (B) Sønder Kohave → 256 (A) Bangsebro Skov

The Forest Corridor II

256 (B) Sønder Kohave → 256 (A) Bangsebro Skov → 175 Listrup Lyng

The proposal for these corridors is planting three forest habitat types—plant species of oak and beech, as well as species *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior* found in the alluvial forest habitat—all of which are shared among all areas involved. The reason for it would be that the ideal conditions for both bats include forest habitats, and that the proposed species are already present in the areas intended to connect. Existing waterways and walking paths will be used to create these corridors; the trees will be planted along said waterways and walking paths up to 2 meters on each side. Since the Barbastelle bat (*Barbastella barbastellus*) is not found in Listrup Lyng, the goal would be to ensure ideal habitat conditions in the corridor leading to that area so that the bat could expand its distribution and be present there as well. Additionally, there

are six more habitats which 175 Listrup Lyng and anchor area 173 have in common: Luzulo-Fagetum beech forests, hard oligo-mesotrophic waters, natural dystrophic lakes and ponds, alkaline fens, species-rich *Nardus* grasslands, and *Molinia* meadows. This information could be useful to increase the species diversity on the corridor, however more research should take place to ensure the feasibility and functionality of these additions.

Urban greening

The corridors connecting the nature areas of the West Side must pass through the matrix of urbanized and industrialized land. This urban area, which includes residential, commercial, and municipal space creates an environment that threatens the movement of species between the coastal anchor and the inland nature sites. Therefore, the connectivity proposal which extends through this area must be urban-specific to expand the canopy cover and transform the gray infrastructure into hybrid and green infrastructure. The main proposal would be to plant beech and oak trees in tree beds, rain gardens, and tree lines along streets and pathways and the harborside. Specific tree species, especially oak (Sæbø et al., 2003), have been proven to thrive in urban conditions due to their structural attributes and their resistance to the threats of the urban environment.

Other measures to protect the bat that could be put in place are allowing them to roost and breed in human structures such as roofs and basements in buildings and monitoring them to ensure their survival and wellbeing and to observe whether the measures improve its population. Human structures can be optimal places for bats, often chosen for their proximity to abundant food sources and because of the houses' unique roosting facilities. The Nature Agency claims that, in about 90% of cases, there are minimal to no disturbances of having bats in the house and recommend embracing having nature close by (Naturstyrelsen, 2025). Only when smell or noise is too much of a nuisance can the bat be evicted, which is strongly recommended to elicit the assistance of a wildlife specialist. From the 1980s, the mammal section of the zoological

museum in Copenhagen has assisted over 3000 house owners that co-live with bats (Naturstyrelsen, 2025).

East side

The areas 175 Listrup Lyng, 175 Horreby Lyng, 257 Halskov Vænge and anchor area 168 have more variability in terms of the habitats and species they share. The bat species present in the west side Zone (the Barbastelare bat) is also present in this zone. The dragonfly *Leucorrhinia pectoralis*, commonly called large white-faced darter, is another animal species that is shared between more than one area. In terms of habitats, there are fourteen that are found in more than one area, which makes them potentially useful for the corridors. There are some areas that do not have common habitats with the closest areas but do share them with other areas further away.

The anchor area 168 is found further north from the project area, but it can and should be connected to the protected areas through Corselitze Skov, because of their shared ecological characteristics. Corselitze Skov is a privately-owned coastal forest on the east coast of Falster. It mainly consists of deciduous trees (including beech and oak), as well as conifers. Both corridors on the east side, the Dragonfly Corridor and the Bat Corridor, connect to Corselitze Skov which then connects to anchor area 168 (see *Figure 20*).

It is recommended to re-create a new functional acroterm, which are living mosses (Especially *Sphagnum* sp.) mixed with seed plants adapted to very wet poor-nutrient conditions. In this way, it is important to create a favorable environment to promote Sphagnum growth (Van Andel & Aronson, 2012). Nonetheless, we also observed some natural succession, especially by tree species, such as Birch (*Betula* sp.) and pine (*Pinus contorta*), which is consistent with other restoration studies for bogs and also an important threat for the appropriate formation of bogs (Vítovcová et al., 2021). This is a common problem that has been registered before and the main problem is the high costs of managing them (Andersen et al., 2016).

It is worth mentioning that there are three species of birds that are only found in 175 Listrup Lyng: the bittern (*Botaurus stellaris*), the marsh-harrier (*Circus aeruginosus*) and the crane (*Grus grus*). Even if they are not currently found in any other area, these species will benefit from the corridors created, especially the ones by the waterways, since they prefer freshwater habitats. With this, the goal would be to expand their distribution beyond Listrup Lyng.

The Dragonfly Corridor

175 Listrup Lyng → 175 Horreby Lyng → Anchor 168

The commonality between these areas is the presence of the dragonfly *Leucorrhinia pectoralis*. Using riparian forests tree species found in the alluvial forest habitat present in all these areas, including *Alnus glutinosa* and *Fraxinus excelsior*, along the waterways and by the freshwater formations would help create the ideal conditions for the dragonfly to migrate from one area to another, and possibly expand its distribution range in the long term.

There is an area by the western side of Horreby Lyng which is indicated as an undesirable afforestation area by the municipality (see *Figure 14*), which is why this corridor is shaped the way it is in the southwest of 175 Horreby Lyng (see *Figure 20*). Most of the corridor has been modified to include the desirable afforestation area, as the plan is to plant tree species. However, another scenario would be to have the corridor include the undesirable afforestation area and instead have the implementation measures be to introduce habitats more suitable for the wet conditions of Horreby Lyng (Pedersen, 2013). Initially the area would be managed as a meadow, which with time will turn into a bog, the ideal condition for the species and habitat present. The challenges of varying timescales like this are discussed later.

The Bat Corridor

175 Horreby Lyng → 257 Halskov Vænge → Corselitze / Anchor 168

The Barbastelle bat is the only animal species that these areas have in common. Therefore, the primary focus for this corridor is enhancing this bat's habitat. The idea would be to install boulders and deadwood, preserve future deadwood, as well as planting tree species that will eventually grow to old canopy. Moreover, leaving some old buildings and other possibly abandoned structures would further improve the bat's habitat and distribution. Halskov Vænge is very close to the anchor area 168, so the measures would consist in protecting and monitoring the three habitats and the bat.

In terms of the species used for the corridors, there is the inconvenience that Horreby Lyng and Halskov Vænge do not have any common habitats. However, Listrup Lyng and Halskov Vænge do share three habitats (Asperulo-Fagetum beech forests, Sub-Atlantic and medio-European oak or oak-hornbeam forests, and species-rich *Nardus* grasslands), which are the exact same as the ones in common between Halskov Vænge and anchor area 168. Therefore, these species could be planted along the corridors from Horreby Lyng to Halskov Vænge and to anchor area 168. More specifically, the species of beech and oak would create a forest landscape with the ideal conditions for the bat population to thrive. The alluvial forest species planted in the Dragonfly Corridor would also benefit the Barbastelle bat population as well, as it fits their preferred habitat characteristics.

South Side

The South Stepping Stones

256 Sønder Kohave and Bangsebro Skov → Anchor 168

In the southern part of the project area, there are a few small nature areas of lakes, bogs, peat meadows and peat mosses with the potential to become stepping stones. Even though they are not under the Natura 2000 protection, they are protected areas under Section 3 of the Nature Conservation Act in Denmark (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2022; Promulgation of the Nature Conservation Act, 2024), and therefore are fitting to include in the corridors plan. The proposed measures regarding these small areas would lean more towards protecting and

conserving them to ensure that species can use them as stepping stones and that the habitats are not degraded or lost in any way.

As previously stated, the Barbastelle bat is found in all the areas except for Listrup Lyng, and the stepping stones would enhance connectivity not only between the two anchor sites, but also among all the other areas where this species is present: Sønder Kohave and Bangsebro Skov, Horreby Lyng and Halskov Vænge. Furthermore, the pond bat would benefit from this increased connectivity as well as all the other measures for the Barbastelle bat, since they benefit bat populations in general. Potentially, the pond bat would expand its distribution to other protected nature areas within the project's scope and beyond. The dragonfly species could also potentially use the stepping stones, since the habitat conditions would be ideal for them. The three species of birds found only in Listrup Lyng could benefit from them as well and increase their distribution across the project area. In general, these stepping stones would improve connectivity across the Falster Island and potentially help many species, beyond those protected, to thrive and expand.

Discussion, reflections and limitations

Stakeholder Engagement and Partnerships in Monitoring

On the Island of Falster, most of the matrix is controlled by private landowners. In many cases, private landowners are unaware of the dire need to reconnect the habitats that surround their properties, and they may not be informed on the multiple benefits that can come from such a plan of green infrastructure in their own backyards (Water Environment Federation, 2014). Therefore, they may not actively choose to strategically rewild parts of their land or build out green infrastructure projects, without guidance or partnership of the municipality or a larger organization that has the purpose of decreasing landscape fragmentation. While fragmentation can be seen as more of a municipal or national management issue rather than private landowner management issue, if landowners have the opportunity to participate in projects with

the purpose of shrinking fragmentation, the question is if they would have the desire to participate.

Given that the success of land use changes often hinges on local support, it is in the municipality's best interest to actively engage private landowners in the development and implementation of such plans. Building awareness around the presence of unique and vulnerable species that inhabit these areas—and highlighting how their vulnerability is connected to fragmentation—can foster a sense of shared responsibility and strengthen stewardship among landowners. This can be achieved through community workshops, canvassing, educational materials and the creation of participatory platforms that encourage dialogue between residents, conservation experts and municipal planners. Mosaic governance is a method where municipalities evolve their governance role into that of a more collaborative partner, supporting co-creation and participatory decision making, where landowners and other stakeholders can meet and collaborate (Bagchi et al., 2024). Xu et al. (2019) conducted a review focusing on 92 different cultural and natural landscape corridors in Europe where they concluded that planning approaches for corridors could be more elaborate and diverse by including different types of stakeholders in the planning process. Another study in Greece, aiming to increase connectivity between N2000 areas regarding the wolf, highlights the importance of the collaboration between the municipality, the authorities and the stakeholders for achieving a successful land use and landscape planning, nature conservation and sustainable development (Votsi et al., 2015). By involving landowners in the process and demonstrating the ecological and social value of preserving these habitats, municipalities can build lasting partnerships that contribute to the long-term success of conservation and land management goals.

SPOR pathways is a national program that exemplifies how private landowners are already not only collaborating with nature protection and expansion but are also contributing their own land to the cause. It is a project first launched in 1997, and which currently has over 300 walking trails across the whole of Denmark (SPOR, 2025). The project has been supported by the Nordea fund since 2015, and for the period 2020 to 2025 the project has received 4,57 million DKK. Participation in the project by the

landowners is on a voluntary basis (Nordea-fonden, 2020). These landowners are likely to have a positive attitude on projects focused on nature and biodiversity as they are already participating in SPOR which aims to get more people out in nature. This program sheds light on the potential of cooperation between private, industry and other landowners within the matrix in the mission to connect nature areas (SPOR, 2025).

The success of the Green Tripartite has been dependent on dialogue, mutual consensus and shared responsibility between the national government, municipalities, industry stakeholders and labour unions. The kind of cross-sectorial cooperation and collaboration that The Green Tripartite exemplifies should be aspired to in a transboundary project such as this. Measuring and monitoring of the structural effectiveness of the corridors can also be a component of community-based cooperation. The IUCN reiterates the notion that to achieve a functional network of ecological corridors, the structural makeup must be scientifically appropriate (Hilty et al., 2020). As natural areas span swaths of land, and there are seemingly endless indicators that can be measured, initiatives of citizen science can be extremely helpful in monitoring habitats. The GIS layer of species observations on page 41 is an example of how citizen science can help inform policy. Additionally, in the case of citizen science, it will be important to target analysis on relevant information that will validate or dictate changes in landscape management schemes. From a baseline measurement into the future, has overall soil, air and ecosystem quality improved? Have protected species been observed more frequently? Has an increase in nature corridors made the landscape more resilient to climate change? Asking questions such as these, and finding which indicators are worth measuring to answer these questions, is what makes citizen science powerful.

To be able to realize this proposal plan for establishing natural corridors between Natura 2000 areas on Falster, a viable economic pathway is necessary to secure the 'buy-in' of the landowners who farm their land. An option is to participate in the newly introduced eco-schemes under the Common Agricultural Policy 2023-2027. Landowners who practice agriculture on their land and receive subsidies through the

EU CAP have the opportunity to participate in eco-schemes through the CAP pillar I. By doing so, they could dedicate the necessary area to obtain structural connectivity outlined in the corridor proposal and simultaneously get financial compensation for their now unproductive agricultural area. By participating in both the CAP eco-schemes and connecting Natura 2000 areas on Falster and thereby strengthening local biodiversity, landowners receive financial compensation and get to contribute to combatting biodiversity loss in their local community.

In line with IUCN guidelines, another recommendation may be to create a voluntary conservation agreement with specific landowners and rights holders (Hilty et al., 2020). Affected landowners can be categorized into three distinct categories depending on the characteristics of their land as follows: landowners with land including high nature values, landowners whose land has no existing nature values, and landowners voluntarily participating in SPOR. From here, conservation agreements can be met. If the landowner falls into the first category and has HNV areas on its land, the eco-schemes present an opportunity to get financial compensation for those areas and thereby minimizing the incentive to change their land use. These HNV areas could also be protected under Section 3 of the Planning Act, making changes to its current state illegal.

More concurrent social and economic benefits worth investigating include benefits for current landowners including farmers, creating increased recreation opportunities and potential for tourism. Regarding landowners who currently have no existing nature values on their land, we evaluate that participation in the eco-schemes becomes highly relevant due to agricultural areas being converted into nature. The same applies for landowners who voluntarily participate in SPOR. The initiative proposed above for these areas are to plant trees in a 2 m zone on each side of the walking trails. Furthermore, uptake of the eco-schemes has been suboptimal in Denmark, with only about 60% of the budget utilized, therefore there are a magnitude of opportunities to be explored regarding eco-schemes (Højte et al., 2024).

Clearly, for successful implementation to be feasible, meaningful cooperation between the municipality and affected landowners is critical. In the case of this project, the municipality considered it a necessity to have the final corridor proposal ready before interacting with potential landowners, and because of the nature of this project schedule, we could not include landowners in a meaningful manner in this project.

Varying Time Horizons

One of the biggest challenges for this project is managing the difference in time scales and time horizons within the project. For example, the formation of the Dragonfly Corridor, specifically the areas designated for raised bogs, will be on a much different timescale than the construction of green infrastructure in the urban areas, as they are one of the most difficult habitats to restore. Regarding the time that could take for this bog corridor to be successfully functional is uncertain. One study had done efforts to restore a bog for thirty years with not many beneficial results (Vítovcová et al., 2021). Despite this, other study suggests the use of mosses micro-propagated in laboratory as gel and plugs have shown between 95-99% of survival and establishment in fields as long as the environment is kept protected and moist (especially by restoring hydrological processes of the area), but it is important to highlight that these methods -although successful- could be more expensive as they must be considered as a long-term restoration process (Caporn et al., 2018).

With respect to the time dimension to the forest corridor, some studies point out that the restoration of deciduous forests could take between 20 years (McLachlan & Bazely, 2003) to centuries (Vasseur, 2012), depending on the current environmental conditions, such as soil and previous land use. Also, its restoration will require high management and monitoring, especially using adaptive management strategies (Vasseur, 2012).

It is likely that, initially, green infrastructure projects will need to be maintained on a regular basis, similarly to regular maintenance of gray infrastructure. But green infrastructure projects are usually most vulnerable to destruction in their first few years and become more self-sufficient as they mature (Water Environment Federation,

2014). Short to medium-term management and monitoring schemes should be developed for projects such as these.

Alignment with Literature and Past Research

For the Green Map of Denmark, there are three national criteria that have to be followed when areas are designated, one of which is that the designated areas have to have synergy effects regarding climate adaptation, the water environment or recreational opportunities (Styrelsen for Grøn Arealomlægning og Vandmiljø, 2017b). By utilizing the Green Map of Denmark as one of the foundational GIS layers, we are acknowledging and incorporating the existing science-backed analysis on the area's ecosystem status into our proposal, thereby making it more robust.

Due to the multiple policies, frameworks and strategies presented in the literature review, most prominently the newly adopted Green Tripartite, Denmark has committed to establishing a 250.000 ha new forest. It will be the municipalities that are responsible for identifying afforestation areas and establishing the new forests. By implementing the corridors suggested in this paper, a substantial amount of new nature will be introduced to Falster via land use change. To quantify the additional ha of forest, one would have to know the tree species planted, how large that tree will grow in its life cycle, space needed between trees and the length and width of the corridor. Although these calculations are not performed in this paper, we can confidently conclude that the corridor proposal will add a considerable amount of new nature to Guldborgsund Municipalities areas and contribute a significant portion in reaching their political and environmental goals.

Scope Limitations and Perspectives on Further Research

There were many reasons why we decided to focus on area 257, 175, 256 and consider 173 and 168 as anchors. First, there was an important lack of time for us to visit both the N2000 areas and the surroundings during our excursion. This decision was crucial as it was necessary to observe the surroundings together with the current state of the N2000 areas so that we could decide the best places to trace the line for pathways. This is why we excluded the N2000 areas in Lolland and only focused on Falster. Areas

173 and 168 by themselves were the biggest in regards to species and habitats present, and land and water cover, so it was preferable to use them as anchors to connect the smallest and most isolated areas to a bigger one and enhance the state of the habitats and increase biodiversity.

Had time and scope limitations not been an issue and all Natura 2000 areas could have been included, the following would have been interesting to research further. Area 174 Maltrup Skov protects four different habitats, Luzulo-Fagetum beech forests, Asperulo-Fagetum beech forests, oak forests and alluvial forests, and one species, the *Osmoderma eremita*. The protected habitats are identical to the ones in the Forest Corridor with the exception of Luzulo-Fagetum beech forests. This presents the opportunity of connecting Area 174 Maltrup Skov to the Forest Corridor. Furthermore, the *Osmoderma eremita* is present in the anchor area 173 which splits Lolland and Falster. Area 176 Krenkerup Skov protects three different habitats and two different species, the *Osmoderma eremita* and the Barbastelle bat. The protected habitats are all identical to the ones in the Forest Corridor, so the opportunity to connect this area to the corridor is also present and would need further research. By connecting these two areas on Lolland to the Forest Corridor on Falster via the anchor area 173, the species *Osmoderma eremita* and Barbastelle bat could have the opportunity to disperse to new areas.

Area 177 Maribosøerne is located on the border of Guldborgsund and Lolland Municipalities, with most of the area being within the borders of Lolland Municipalities. This area protects 17 different habitats and 16 different species, 13 of which are different bird species. This area shares three bird species in common with Area 175 Listrup Lyng: the Eurasian Bittern, the Western Marsh-harrier, and the Common Crane. In addition to this, Maribosøerne also protects ten more bird species. Future research is needed to explore the most optimal connection focusing on birds, so they have the opportunity of increasing their dispersal. A cross-municipal partnership would be necessary in the planning, implementation and management process of the area. This type of collaboration can also include local stakeholders and landowners to enrich a transboundary, trans-sector partnership to connect and protect natural areas.

Finally, it was observed during field work that the dominant land use type surrounding the Natura 2000 areas are agricultural fields. Børgesen (2015) reveals that around 13 different herbicides have the highest concentration in Falster's soil compared to the rest of Denmark, especially due to sweet beet crops. Based on this information, and in addition to *Figure 15*, we express our concern regarding the effect of soil pollution over the health of the habitats and biodiversity by pesticides as, in general, it is one of the main causes of soil contamination (Cachada et al., 2018; European Environment Agency, 2024). We suggest future measurements and monitoring to assess the mitigation of soil contamination, especially close to Natura 2000 areas, so the efforts to protect the habitats and biodiversity can maximize their effectiveness. Additionally, baseline data should be taken from all the sites to establish a baseline before conservation efforts are implemented. There also should be an understanding of the fluidity and unpredictability of nature, especially in the context of climate change.

Conclusion

Our final proposal is the result of a multi-layered spatial analysis, bolstered by ecological, environmental, spatial and policy considerations. Our methodology combined habitat and species analysis, on-site observations, aggregations of various land use and environmental geo datasets, and political theory to create and implement a set of criteria that could inform a nature connectivity proposal for the Island of Falster. In design and analysis workshops we were able to overlay environmental layers on maps to identify areas of interest; in integrating species-specific habitat requirements into that design, we identified the most suitable corridor conditions for species that are listed protected under the EU's Habitats Directive and Birds Directive. This approach allowed us to address our initial problem formulation by investigating the habitat conditions within the Natura 2000 areas, assessing the ecological needs of the protected species they support, and analyzing land use patterns in the surrounding landscape matrix. In doing so, we identified optimal opportunities for corridor

development by leveraging existing features such as waterways and walking paths, while also considering, in a preliminary and speculative manner, how specific landowners might be engaged in the implementation of such a connectivity plan.

The proposed corridor network consists of four distinct ecological corridors within three zones of Falster, primarily focusing on habitats such as raised bogs, deciduous forests and riparian forests. These habitat types are essential for several protected species, and for the greater ecological health of the Island. Each corridor was designed to support and enhance the ecological needs of specific species while also having the hope of creating habitats for more diverse species.

We conclude that successful implementation will require a mixture of immediate green infrastructure installation and long-term restoration and management efforts for complex ecosystems. Planning must be done to meaningfully engage with landowners and other relevant stakeholders to ensure the long-term success and ecological effectiveness of the proposed connectivity network.

A connected network of Natura 2000 areas holds significantly greater ecological value than isolated sites standing alone, as it enhances the resilience of ecosystems and improves the conservation prospects for threatened species by encouraging movement and expansion. Strengthening connectivity between the Natura 2000 areas on the Island of Falster is essential and possible for addressing both biodiversity loss and the challenges posed by climate change (Kalfas et al., 2024).

Finally, there is no single, universally correct set of criteria for guiding restoration work of this kind. However, it is our hope that this project serves as a practical example for how landscape and nature management techniques can be integrated to implement a comprehensive, science-based management strategy.

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